

visited. Where the disease was present, samples were taken to determine its incidence. From each 1-m² plot, samples were taken at random to represent roughly 10% of the total area, except at Balansera and Mapotolon where only 3 samples were collected. For each sample the number of diseased and healthy hills was recorded and the total number of diseased and healthy tillers in each diseased hill was noted (see table). ❧

Studies on rice tungro virus disease and its vector *Nephotettix* spp. in West Bengal, India, in 1976–77

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Rice green leafhoppers were collected daily with light traps at the Plant Virus Experimental Field, Kalyani; Habra Model Farm; and Central Soil Salinity Research Institute, Canning, in a study funded by the Indian Council of Agricultural Research.

Leafhoppers were found from April to December at Kalyani, from April to the second week of February at Habra, and throughout the year at Canning. The peak population differed slightly from location to location. The peak appeared during the third week of October at Kalyani, during the second week of October at Canning, and during the first week of November at Habra.

At the peak period, the greatest number of leafhoppers was found at Habra where the insects averaged 1,129/day. The average at the peak period was 913/day at Kalyani, and 339/day at Canning. There were more *Nephotettix virescens* than *N. nigropictus*. More males of *N. virescens* appeared during the peak period, but during the remaining period females predominated.

Weeds were collected from sites where tungro virus disease had been previously observed. *Echinochloa colonum* was predominant. Transmission studies during boro 1976–77 showed that the weeds did not carry any virus. But when inoculated, they can retain the virus for more than

2 months as a symptomless carrier. Adult leafhoppers fed on *E. colonum* could not survive more than 120 hours. Infected stubble obtained from the 1976 kharif crop and transplanted in pots retained the virus for more than 90 days. But under cage conditions the virus could not be transmitted by releasing nonviruliferous leafhoppers on seedlings growing in soil containing chopped-off stubbles.

The possibility of symptomless rice plants or those with mild symptoms grown in one season acting as the source of the virus during the next was studied. Transmission tests were performed during the 1976–77 boro with IR20, IR30, IR26, IR442-58, Vijaya, Cavery, Ratna, Bala, Krishna, Jaya, Palman, IET 849, and IET 2239. The presence of virus in Jaya was detected although prominent symptoms did not develop during the season. Prominent symptoms developed in IET 849, IET 2239, and Palman.

The relationship between vector population and tungro virus spread in the fields was studied. The leafhopper population differed among locations in both number and time of appearance. In the study of the natural occurrence of viruliferous leafhoppers, 50% of the leafhoppers collected from fields showing virus symptoms carried the virus; leafhoppers from normal fields appeared to be virus free during the period of observation. ❧

Operational research on sheath blight control

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Eight promising foliar fungicides belonging to different groups were tested in farmers' fields during rabi 1977–78 to determine their control of rice sheath blight. Two sites in each of two villages were selected for the study. The experimental area in each site was 14.6 ha (36 acres).

Plots treated with benlate (benzimidazole), difolatan (heterocyclic nitrogen compound), or hinosan (organo-phosphorus compound) had

Mean sheath blight disease scores and yield in plots treated with 8 fungicides. Kerala, India, 1977–78.

Treatment	Mean score ^a (0–9)	Mean yield (t/ha)
Benlate	0.56	6.03
Captan	4.61	5.54
Cuman - L	2.38	5.29
Difolatan	1.24	5.38
Dithane M - 45	1.70	5.51
Fytolan	2.69	5.23
Hinosan	1.40	5.74
Kitazin	2.01	5.44
Untreated control	4.63	5.36
CD P ± 0.05	1.10	NS

^a 0 = no infection; 9 = severe infection.

significantly lower disease scores than the control (see table). Plots treated with other chemicals also showed lower disease scores. Grain yields in treated plots generally increased. Plots treated with benlate had the highest yield. ❧

Rice ragged stunt in Thailand

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Ragged stunt disease of rice in Thailand was observed for the first time in a farmer's field at Chacheongsao province in 1977. Experiments were carried out to determine the manner in which the disease was transmitted.

Sections of the infected plants collected from the farmer's field were examined by Dr. Y. Saito at the Institute for Plant Virus Research, Japan. The electron micrograph revealed abundant polyhedral particles in phloem cells (photo 1).

Four species of sucking insects naturally found in paddy fields — *Nilaparvata lugens*, *Nephotettix virescens*, *N. nigropictus*, and *Recilia dorsalis* — were fed directly on diseased plants for 3 days, then were transferred to healthy rice seedlings grown in an insect-proof screenhouse. Only the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* could transmit the disease. The infected plants developed symptoms typical of the disease as described by K. C. Ling at IRRI.